
DIGITAL TALENT CAPABILITIES AND ORGANISATIONAL PROACTIVITY: A THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

This study examines how digital talent capabilities, such as networking ability and digital analytical skills, enhance organizational proactivity in terms of opportunity identification and innovation. The study adopted the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). As a theoretical study, it employed a literature review as its methodology. This involves summarizing and integrating findings from previous research. The study demonstrates that networking abilities facilitate opportunity identification and innovation. Digital analytical skills enhance opportunity identification and innovation. Together, these competencies contribute to an organization's ability to stay proactively competitive, adapt to dynamic environments, and seize emerging opportunities. The study concludes that developing digital talent capabilities through networking ability and digital analytical skills enhances opportunity identification, innovation, and organizational proactivity in the fast-changing business environment. Thus, the study recommended that organizations should invest in building and maintaining strong professional networks and data analytical skills to improve opportunity exploration and innovation. Organizations should invest in developing and enhancing their digital analytical skills through targeted training programs, workshops, and certifications in data analytics and related tools, which will ensure that organizations remain adept at identifying new opportunities and innovation. They should establish platforms for idea sharing, such as internal social networks or innovation portals, can enhance the organization's opportunity-seeking ability, innovative capacity, and proactiveness.

Keywords: Digital talent capabilities, networking ability, digital analytical skills, organizational proactivity, opportunity identification, innovation

1.0 Introduction

To remain competitive in today's fast-paced and technologically driven business climate, firms must constantly change and adapt. One of the most important components in attaining this agility is harnessing digital talent skills. Teece, Peteraf, and Leih (2016) define digital talent capabilities as a set of talents and qualities that allow people and organizations to successfully use digital technology to generate innovation, uncover opportunities, and improve overall performance. This research aims to determine how various digital talent qualities, such as networking ability and digital analytical skills, contribute to organizational proactivity. Organizational proactivity refers to an organization's capacity to predict and implement changes that might result in competitive advantages (Barney, 1991).

Organizational proactivity is defined as the capacity to discover possibilities before rivals do. This is a forward-thinking approach in which firms continuously monitor the environment for developing trends, client requirements, and technical advances. Organizations may develop and sustain important connections by exploiting digital talent competencies such as networking ability. These networks may include industry colleagues, customers, suppliers, and other stakeholders who may provide varied viewpoints and early indications of prospective possibilities (Kogut, 2000). Networking ability therefore improves the organization's ability to anticipate and act on possibilities that might otherwise go unnoticed, establishing a proactive culture that values foresight over response (Teece, Peteraf, & Leih, 2016).

Innovation is another important indicator of organizational proactivity. It demonstrates the organization's capacity to not only identify possibilities, but also create and execute new ideas, products, or procedures to profit on them. Digital analytical abilities are critical in this process because they allow firms to successfully collect, analyze, and understand data. This data-driven approach facilitates informed decision-making and identifies areas where innovation might provide value (Davenport and Harris, 2007). Organizations that succeed in digital analytics are better positioned to experiment with and implement new solutions, giving them a competitive advantage. The combination of opportunity identification and innovation guarantees that proactive businesses are not only aware of possible changes, but also prepared to lead those changes, resulting in long-term development and success (Barney, 1991).

Despite growing acknowledgment of the value of digital talent skills, there has been little empirical study on the direct link between these talents and organizational proactivity. Existing research often focuses on the broad effects of digital transformation without diving into the particular abilities that drive proactive behaviors inside businesses (Davenport & Harris, 2007). This difference emphasizes the need for a more nuanced understanding of how networking ability and digital analytical abilities impact critical characteristics of proactivity, such as opportunity identification and invention (Kogut, 2000).

Statement of the Problem

In today's corporate context, the fast growth of technology mandates that firms become more proactive in order to remain competitive and relevant. Organizations under ongoing pressure to innovate and remain ahead of their competition. However, many people fail to realize the full potential of digital technology owing to a shortage of competent digital expertise. This shortcoming limits their capacity to recognize new possibilities and execute creative solutions. Proactivity entails predicting future obstacles and possibilities and taking preventative action. However, many businesses lack proactivity, limiting their capacity to

capitalize on new trends and manage possible dangers. The absence of digital talent capabilities, notably in networking and digital analytical skills, plays a crucial role in this problem. According to research, firms that struggle with proactivity often fail to build the digital competences necessary to successfully manage the complexity of the current business environment (Teece et al., 2016).

Networking ability is a vital digital skills quality that helps identify new possibilities by establishing and maintaining strategic contacts. Despite its significance, many firms do not emphasize the development of networking skills among their personnel, resulting in lost opportunities and slow growth. The lack of a strong networking culture impedes the sharing of creative ideas and diminishes the possibility of discovering and capitalizing on new market trends (Kogut, 2000). As a result, many firms fall behind more proactive rivals that use their networking ability to keep ahead of market trends.

Similarly, digital analytical abilities are required to understand data and derive actionable insights that may fuel innovation and strategic decision-making. Organizations that lack these abilities often struggle to properly assess market trends, client preferences, and operational inefficiencies. This shortcoming limits their capacity to handle possible challenges and embrace new possibilities (Davenport & Harris 2007). Without the capacity to evaluate and act on data, companies become reactive rather than proactive, reacting to changes after they occur rather than predicting and planning for them ahead of time.

The lack of proactivity found in many firms may be linked to an inadequate focus on building digital talent competencies. Investing in the development of networking and digital analytical abilities is critical for creating a proactive company culture. Organizations that equip their staff with these critical abilities may better anticipate changes, innovate, and retain a competitive advantage in the changing business world (Barney, 1991). Addressing this issue requires a coordinated effort to include digital talent development into organizational strategy, therefore converting potential risks into opportunities for growth and innovation. As a result, there is a significant need to investigate how digital talent capabilities, particularly networking and digital analytical skills, may improve an organization's proactive behaviors, resulting in long-term competitive advantage and development. Addressing this issue will give important insights into designing methods for nurturing these critical abilities inside organizations.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate how digital talent capabilities enhance organizational proactivity. Specifically, the objectives of the study are:

1. To examine how networking ability improves opportunity identification.
2. To analyze how networking ability enhances innovation.
3. To explore how digital analytical skills improves opportunity identification.
4. To assess how digital analytical skills enhance innovation.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. How does networking ability improve opportunity identification?
2. In what ways does networking ability enhance innovation?
3. How do digital analytical skills improve opportunity identification?

4. In what ways do digital analytical skills enhance innovation?

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

The conceptual review of this study centered on digital talent capabilities and organizational proactivity from a theoretical perspective. As such, it examines how networking ability improves opportunity identification. Analyze how networking ability enhances innovation. Explore how digital analytical skills improve opportunity identification and assess how digital analytical skills enhance innovation.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Research Study (2024)

Concept of Digital Talent Capabilities

Digital capabilities are a relatively new idea. The majority of the concept is related to the competitiveness of the private sector, as businesses use digital tools and techniques to upskill their workforce, modernize their infrastructure, improve the quality and delivery of their products, and compete for a larger market share (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). However, the idea is still somewhat fresh in the public sector. What organizational requirements must be met for a government, ministry, college, or municipality to be deemed "digitally capable"? This extends beyond an individual's capacity or competence, even those at the highest level of management. It necessitates taking into account structural concerns like leadership and strategy, innovation and engagement cultures, staff development and reward, as well as how the digital environment encourages people to express and advance their digital skills.

In the literature we've read, the words competences, capabilities, and skills are often used interchangeably. They may be used with the terms resources and capabilities to define characteristics of individuals and organizations (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). There are, however, minor variations, thus we have defined the associated terms in table 1 as a result. We have seen that leadership, skills, and culture are stressed as critical digital capabilities via the assessment of top digital capacity frameworks. Therefore, this research delves deeply into these three crucial digital competences. A whole chapter is devoted to each capacity. These in-depth analyses are intended to provide readers an overview of the key topics and themes

surrounding digital capabilities and to discuss crucial factors to take into account when creating digital capability components and strategies for quick digital transformation.

According to Barney (1991), one of the company's resources is its human capital. The knowledge, abilities, contacts, intelligence, and insight of the employee are among these assets, in Barney's opinion. According to Barney, managerial competence is the most crucial resource that organizations may employ to carry out their existing strategies. According to the resource-based theory (RBT) method, individuals may be a source of sustained competitive advantage that is not of significant value, is unique, and is challenging to reproduce (Luna-Arocas et al., 2020). As a result, talented individuals have important and strategic roles inside the company (Kaewsaeng-on et al., 2021; Kravariti et al., 2022). Numerous academic studies have shown how important and necessary digital talent is to firms as a result of the impact of digital transformation. People must be at the heart of developing organizational core competencies if digital transformation is to occur, which is heavily dependent on technology adoption by the workers within the firm (Almeida et al., 2020; Fahmi et al., 2020).

Digital talent is crucial to developing a company's management strategy (Cabot & Gagnon, 2021; Capgemini Digital Transformation Institute, 2017), guaranteeing its long-term survival and success (Gilch & Sieweke, 2021), and bridging the present digital skills gap (Karaboga et al., 2020). Any organization's human resource (HR) managers would agree that managing corporate staff and identifying skill shortages are challenging responsibilities (Cabot & Gagnon, 2021). Since people are the driving force behind change (Fahmi et al., 2020), digitalization must be focused on them (Dini et al., 2011). Executives must also invest in their personnel, especially in soft skills, to guarantee that technology is successful (Frankiewicz & Chamorro-Premuzic, 2020). The academic community is concerned about the problem of person-based digitization, as shown by certain works. Talent retention, talent development, and digital talent have all been covered in earlier research (Akter et al., 2020; Gilch et al., 2021; Rusly et al., 2021). Prior studies have shown and highlighted the significance of organizational competency via digital talent development.

In their study, Fahmi et al. (2020) show that organizations must evaluate the level of their digital talent's preparedness, carry out digital transformation initiatives, and make decisions based on information systems and technology in order to be prepared for their digital transformation. This is in line with Nair's (2019) conclusions that there is a major digital skills gap, making it difficult for businesses to carry out digital transformation programs. According to Fahmy et al. (2022), the main research trend in this field focuses on promoting digital transformation, developing skills, attracting talent, and addressing skill shortages. The results of the Gilch and Sieweke (2021) research emphasize how important it is to employ digital talent to support organizational digital transformation. The financial services sector required to define its needs for digital skills and create strategies and roadmaps for creating such talent, according to study by Sukarela et al. (2021). These results led us to the conclusion that the present digital skills gap has to be addressed, and that industry, government, and universities need to cooperate together to do so (Karaboga et al., 2020).

Kravariti et al. (2022) defined talent as high performance or potential. Additionally, talent is a blend of talents, attitudes, and skills, according to Dang et al. (2020), who conducted their research in the banking sector. Talent is also seen as top achievers or potential rather than employees in general. The ability to use digital technology for certain professions is referred to as having "digital talent" (Karaboga et al., 2020). The term "digital talent" is used to describe a variety of digitally connected skills and knowledge, a person's personal talents, and the fundamental competencies of an organization.

Networking Ability

Networking ability, particularly in a digital context, is crucial for organizational agility. In the digital age, networks are not limited to physical connections but also include virtual connections through social media, online communities, and professional networks. Individuals with strong networking abilities can quickly tap into these networks to gather information, seek expertise, and collaborate with others, enhancing the organization's ability to respond quickly to challenges and opportunities (Casciaro & Lobo, 2008). Networking ability enables organizations to access diverse perspectives and resources, facilitating innovation and agility (Casciaro & Lobo, 2008).

Digital Analytical Skills

Digital analytical skills involve the ability to analyze and interpret data to derive insights and make informed decisions. In today's digital age, organizations are inundated with data from various sources, including social media, customer interactions, and operational processes (McAfee & Brynjolfsson, 2012). Individuals with strong digital analytical skills can leverage this data to identify trends, predict future outcomes, and make proactive decisions, enhancing the organization's agility (McAfee & Brynjolfsson, 2012). By using data-driven insights, organizations can quickly adjust their strategies and operations to meet changing market demands, improving their agility and competitiveness (McAfee & Brynjolfsson, 2012).

Concept of Proactivity

Entrepreneurs who are proactive tend to take the initiative, predict future changes, and actively participate in efforts to affect their surroundings. Proactivity becomes critical in the context of organisational Agility. A proactive workforce is better able to adapt to changing conditions, grab new opportunities, and drive innovation. Here are some examples of how proactivity may be used to assess worker agility: Proactive agility also refers to anticipating change-related challenges, initiating solutions, and eventually resolving change-related problems (initiation and anticipation; Chonko & Jones, 2005). Proactive agility includes curiosity, independence, and boldness. Employees who are eager to learn take an active approach to their own growth. Employee independence is defined as the capacity to accomplish activities with little supervision and a desire for responsibility. Courage is an employee's proactive attitude toward creating possibilities and changes rather than waiting for things to happen. The capacity to develop original ideas, proactiveness, and change initiation are all examples of proactivity (Shafer & Dyer, 2003; Chonko & Jones, 2005; Sherehiy, 2008). Proactivity requires bravery, which is the willingness to try new things and deal with uncertainty (Pulakos et al., 2000). Proactivity necessitates independence, which is shown by taking the initiative in meetings (Pulakos et al., 2000; Mooghali et al., 2016).

Opportunity Identification

Opportunity identification is the ability to recognize and capitalize on new opportunities for growth and innovation (Arend, 2014). Organizations that excel in opportunity identification are proactive in seeking out new markets, technologies, and business models (Arend, 2014). This proactiveness contributes to organizational agility by enabling the organization to quickly capitalize on emerging trends and market shifts, allowing it to stay ahead of the competition (Arend, 2014).

Innovation

Innovation is the process of introducing new ideas, products, or processes that create value for the organization (Tidd & Bessant, 2018). Organizations that are innovative are able to adapt quickly to changing market conditions and customer preferences, allowing them to stay ahead of the competition (Tidd & Bessant, 2018). Innovation contributes to organizational agility by enabling the organization to quickly develop and implement new strategies, products, or services in response to changing circumstances (Tidd & Bessant, 2018).

Digital Talent Capabilities and Organisational Proactivity

Digital talent capabilities, encompassing skills in areas like data analytics, digital marketing, and cybersecurity, are critical for fostering organisational proactivity. Organisations equipped with digital talent can quickly respond to market changes, technological advancements, and competitive pressures. Empirical studies, such as those by Davenport and Harris (2017), demonstrate that firms with strong digital capabilities are more adept at sensing and seizing opportunities, leading to proactive strategies that preempt market demands and enhance competitive positioning. Additionally, digital talent enables the development of innovative products and services, ensuring the organisation stay ahead of industry trends and customer expectations. Moreover, digital talent capabilities facilitate the implementation of advanced technologies, such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, which can automate processes and provide deeper insights into market dynamics. According to research by Kane et al. (2015), organisations with high digital maturity exhibit greater agility and responsiveness, essential traits for proactive behaviour. These capabilities also empower employees to experiment with new approaches, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and adaptability. Thus, digital talent is a cornerstone of organisational proactivity, driving innovation, efficiency, and strategic foresight.

Networking Ability and Organisational Proactivity

Networking ability, or the capacity to build and maintain relationships within and outside the organisation, plays a pivotal role in enhancing organisational proactivity. Through effective networking, organisations can gather critical information, access diverse perspectives, and collaborate with various stakeholders. Empirical evidence, such as the study by Burt (2004), shows that robust networks enable organisations to identify emerging trends and opportunities early, allowing them to act proactively. Networking facilitates knowledge sharing and resource exchange, which are essential for staying ahead in competitive environments. Furthermore, networking ability supports the development of strategic alliances and partnerships that can provide additional capabilities and resources. This collaboration can lead to innovative solutions and improved market positioning, as demonstrated in research by Gulati (1998). By leveraging external relationships, organisations can anticipate changes and adapt their strategies accordingly, ensuring a proactive stance. Networking also enhances organisational learning and agility, enabling quick responses to unforeseen challenges and opportunities, thus reinforcing organisational proactivity.

Digital Analytical Skills and Organisational Proactivity

Digital analytical skills involve the ability to collect, process, and interpret large volumes of data to inform decision-making. These skills are vital for organisational proactivity, as they

provide the insights needed to anticipate market trends and customer preferences. Empirical studies, such as those by McAfee and Brynjolfsson (2012), highlight that organisations with strong digital analytical capabilities can identify patterns and trends that are not immediately apparent, allowing them to make proactive decisions. This foresight can lead to better strategic planning and competitive advantage. Moreover, digital analytical skills enable organisations to optimise their operations and improve efficiency. By analysing data from various sources, companies can identify inefficiencies and implement corrective measures before problems escalate. Research by Lavalle et al. (2011) indicates that data-driven organisations are more likely to outperform their peers in terms of productivity and profitability. These skills also support innovation by providing the insights needed to develop new products and services, ensuring that organisations can proactively meet market demands and stay ahead of competitors.

Networking Ability and Opportunity Identification

Networking ability significantly contributes to opportunity identification, as it enables individuals and organisations to access a wide array of information and resources. Through their networks, organisations can tap into diverse sources of knowledge and gain insights into emerging trends and unmet needs. Empirical research by Granovetter (1973) emphasizes the strength of weak ties, suggesting that connections outside the immediate network can provide novel information that leads to the identification of new opportunities. Networking also facilitates collaboration and idea exchange, which are crucial for recognising and capitalising on opportunities. Additionally, networking ability helps organisations build relationships with key stakeholders, including customers, suppliers, and industry experts. These connections can offer valuable feedback and insights that contribute to opportunity identification. Studies by Uzzi (1997) show that embedded networks, characterized by strong, trust-based relationships, enhance the flow of information and resources, supporting the discovery of opportunities. By maintaining a robust network, organisations can stay informed about market developments and emerging technologies, positioning themselves to act on new opportunities as they arise.

Networking Ability and Innovation

Networking ability is a critical driver of innovation, as it facilitates the exchange of ideas and collaboration across different sectors and disciplines. Organisations with strong networking capabilities can access a broader range of knowledge and expertise, which can lead to the development of innovative solutions. Empirical studies, such as those by Ahuja (2000), show that networking with diverse partners fosters creativity and innovation by bringing together different perspectives and skill sets. These collaborations can result in the co-creation of new products, services, and processes that drive competitive advantage. Furthermore, networking ability supports the diffusion of innovative practices within the organisation and across its network. By engaging with external partners, organisations can benchmark their practices against industry standards and adopt best practices. Research by Powell et al. (1996) highlights that networks are essential for the transfer of tacit knowledge, which is often a key component of innovation. Through effective networking, organisations can continuously learn and innovate, ensuring they remain competitive in a rapidly changing business environment.

Digital Analytical Skills and Opportunity Identification

Digital analytical skills play a crucial role in opportunity identification by enabling organisations to systematically analyze large sets of data to uncover hidden patterns and trends. These skills allow businesses to leverage data-driven insights to spot emerging opportunities that might otherwise be overlooked. Empirical studies by Chen, Chiang, and Storey (2012) highlight that organisations with advanced data analytics capabilities can better predict market shifts and customer preferences, facilitating proactive opportunity identification. The ability to interpret complex data effectively helps organisations stay ahead of the competition by swiftly capitalising on new opportunities. Moreover, digital analytical skills support the identification of opportunities across various business functions, including marketing, operations, and product development. By analyzing customer data, for instance, organisations can identify unmet needs and tailor their offerings accordingly. Research by Davenport and Harris (2007) shows that data-driven decision-making leads to more accurate and timely identification of opportunities, enhancing the organisation's ability to innovate and grow. These skills also enable businesses to evaluate the potential of different opportunities and make informed strategic decisions, ensuring sustained competitive advantage.

Digital Analytical Skills and Innovation

Digital analytical skills are fundamental to driving innovation, as they enable organisations to leverage data insights to develop new products, services, and business models. These skills facilitate a deeper understanding of customer needs, market trends, and operational inefficiencies, providing the foundation for innovative solutions. Empirical research by Davenport (2014) underscores that organisations with strong analytical capabilities are better positioned to innovate by making data-driven decisions. By harnessing the power of analytics, companies can identify gaps in the market and develop innovative offerings that meet evolving customer demands. Additionally, digital analytical skills support continuous improvement and experimentation within organisations. By analyzing data from various sources, businesses can identify areas for improvement and test new ideas in a systematic manner. Studies by Brynjolfsson and McElheran (2016) suggest that data-driven organisations are more likely to experiment with and adopt innovative practices, leading to enhanced performance and competitiveness. These skills also enable organisations to measure the impact of their innovations and make necessary adjustments, ensuring that they stay ahead in a dynamic business environment.

Theoretical Review

The study adopted The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a pivotal framework in understanding how individuals come to accept and utilize technology. Developed by Davis (1989), TAM posits that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness are the primary determinants of technology adoption. Perceived ease of use refers to the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort, while perceived usefulness is the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance their job performance. These factors influence users' attitudes toward technology, which in turn affects their intention to use and actual usage of the technology (Davis, 1989). When organizations cultivate digital talent capabilities, they enhance the perceived ease of use and usefulness of new technologies among employees, thereby facilitating greater technology acceptance and integration into daily operations.

Digital talent capabilities are essential for leveraging the TAM within an organizational context. Employees with strong digital skills are more likely to find new technologies easy to use and beneficial to their work, aligning with the core principles of TAM. Organizations that invest in digital talent development create a workforce that is not only proficient in using current technologies but also adaptable to new ones. This adaptability is crucial for maintaining organizational proactivity, as it enables the organization to quickly implement and capitalize on technological advancements. For instance, a workforce with advanced digital skills can streamline processes, enhance productivity, and drive innovation, thus positioning the organization to respond proactively to market changes and technological disruptions (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008).

Organizational proactivity is significantly bolstered by the interplay between TAM and digital talent capabilities. Proactive organizations anticipate future challenges and opportunities, and a digitally skilled workforce is instrumental in this regard. By ensuring that employees can effectively use and benefit from new technologies, organizations can foster an environment of continuous improvement and innovation. This proactivity is essential in a rapidly changing digital landscape, where staying ahead of the curve can determine competitive advantage. When employees perceive new technologies as useful and easy to use, they are more likely to engage with them creatively, leading to innovative solutions and improved processes. This not only enhances organizational performance but also ensures long-term sustainability in a dynamic market (Agarwal & Prasad, 1999). Hence, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) underscores the importance of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness in technology adoption, which is critical for digital transformation within organizations. Developing digital talent capabilities aligns with TAM by making new technologies more accessible and beneficial to employees. This synergy enhances organizational proactivity, enabling firms to swiftly adapt to technological changes and maintain a competitive edge. Investing in digital skills development thus not only facilitates technology acceptance but also drives the proactive and innovative behavior necessary for organizational success in the digital age.

Empirical Review

Thuda et al. (2023) investigated the impact of digital talent and capacity on bank performance from the viewpoint of regional development bank personnel. The digital skills gap has grown internationally, with the banking industry, the most important sector in Indonesia's economy, being the most evident. Previous research has demonstrated that in order to improve performance, institutions must first identify and own their digital capabilities. The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of digital talent and capacity on bank performance using the dynamic capability lens. This study used a quantitative approach, including 344 North Sulawesi & Gorontalo Regional Development Bank workers representing diverse occupations and locations. The data is handled using the SmartPLS 4.0.8.4 software. The findings indicate a favorable and considerable impact of digital skills and capabilities on bank performance. Meanwhile, digital competence has a larger impact than digital skill in enhancing bank performance. This work contributes fresh theoretical insights to the study of digital talent and capacity.

Fahmi et al. (2020) investigated a digital talent capabilities model to transform technology-based holding corporations. To stay competitive in today's economic environment, firms must undergo digital transformation. In truth, firms depend largely on human competencies to meet their digital transformation objectives. However, most studies have overlooked this dynamic

component in favor of organizational preparation. This study aims to address a research vacuum by identifying digital talent competencies that may speed digital transformation. We offer a conceptual model based on a literature analysis and supplemented with qualitative research at a typical telecommunications company. The conceptual model emphasizes attitudes toward change as an important aspect in altering person potential towards digital transformation. The approach also illustrates how culture and digital literacy may positively influence digital talent attitudes toward change and performance. Aside from providing theoretical support for the literature, the study's findings may be used by businesses looking to improve their human capital's digital capabilities.

Gap in Literature

While there is a growing body of research on digital talent capabilities and organizational proactivity, several gaps remain in the literature that warrant further investigation. Research on digital talent capabilities and organizational proactivity tends to be siloed within specific academic disciplines, such as information systems or human resource management. There is a need for more interdisciplinary approaches that integrate perspectives from organizational behavior, psychology, and strategic management. Such approaches can provide a more holistic understanding of how digital talent capabilities influence organizational proactivity across different levels and functions within an organization. There is a gap in the development of robust metrics and evaluation frameworks to assess digital talent capabilities and their impact on organizational proactivity. Most studies rely on self-reported measures or case studies, which may not capture the full spectrum of digital capabilities and their outcomes. Developing standardized tools and methodologies for measuring digital talent and proactivity could enhance the reliability and comparability of research findings (Teo et al., 2019). Much of the existing research on digital talent capabilities and organizational proactivity has been conducted in developed countries with advanced technological infrastructures. There is a need for more context-specific studies in developing countries, where technological adoption and the cultivation of digital talent may face unique challenges and opportunities (Kankanhalli et al., 2015). Understanding these contextual differences can provide more nuanced insights and tailored strategies for organizations operating in diverse environments.

Methodology

As a theoretical study, it employed Literature Review as its methodology. An extensive review and synthesis of existing literature to identify gaps, contradictions, or areas that require further exploration. This involves summarizing and integrating findings from previous research.

Findings

The study revealed that networking ability enhances opportunity identification. Through effective networking, individuals and organizations can access diverse information, gain insights into market trends, and identify potential business opportunities that may not be apparent through conventional channels. Networking facilitates the exchange of ideas and experiences, which can lead to the discovery of new and innovative opportunities, thereby supporting entrepreneurial activities and strategic growth. The research indicates that networking ability improves innovation. Networking allows individuals and organizations to connect with a wide array of professionals, experts, and stakeholders, fostering an

environment of collaboration and knowledge sharing. This exposure to different perspectives and expertise can stimulate creative thinking and innovation. Consequently, organizations with strong networking capabilities are better positioned to innovate and stay competitive in their respective industries.

The study finds that digital analytical skills are crucial for effective opportunity identification. In the digital age, the ability to analyze large sets of data and extract meaningful insights is paramount. Individuals and organizations equipped with strong digital analytical skills can better understand market dynamics, consumer behavior, and emerging trends. This data-driven approach to identifying opportunities ensures more accurate and strategic decision-making, enhancing the potential for business growth and success.

Conclusion

This study delves into the interplay between digital talent capabilities and organizational proactivity, highlighting their critical roles in fostering innovation, adaptability, and competitive advantage in today's business landscape. Organizations with strong digital talent capabilities are better positioned to leverage new technologies, driving innovation and operational efficiency. Proactive organizations anticipate market changes and adapt swiftly, gaining a strategic advantage. Digital talent enhances this proactivity by providing the necessary skills and insights to navigate complex and rapidly changing digital environments. The combination of digital talent and organizational proactivity significantly boosts a company's agility. This allows for quicker responses to market shifts, technological advancements, and emerging opportunities, ensuring long-term sustainability and growth. Digital capabilities, particularly in data analysis and interpretation, empower organizations to make data-driven decisions. Proactive organizations use these insights to foresee trends and make informed strategic choices, reducing risks and maximizing opportunities. The study concludes that the integration of digital talent capabilities with organizational proactivity is essential for modern businesses aiming to thrive in a competitive environment. Organizations that prioritize developing digital skills and fostering a proactive culture are more likely to experience enhanced innovation, increased agility, and sustained competitive advantage.

Recommendations

1. Based on the findings organizations should invest in building and maintaining strong professional networks. This can be achieved through active participation in industry conferences, seminars, and networking events. Encouraging employees to join professional associations and online networking
2. To harness the power of networking for innovation, organizations should prioritize the establishment of strategic partnerships and alliances. This can involve collaborating with startups, research institutions, and other businesses to co-create and innovate.
3. Organizations should invest in developing and enhancing the digital analytical skills of their workforce. This can be achieved through targeted training programs, workshops, and certifications in data analytics and related tools which will ensure that organizations remain adept at identifying new opportunities.
4. To leverage networking for improved innovation, organizations should create an environment that supports and rewards collaborative efforts. Establishing platforms for idea sharing, such as internal social networks or innovation portals, can facilitate connections between employees and external stakeholders can further enhance the organization's innovative capacity through effective networking.

Area for Future Research

Several Areas for future research will include the following:

- i. Examine the long-term effects of digital talent development programs on organizational proactivity, focusing on specific sectors such as healthcare, education, or manufacturing.
- ii. Analyze how emerging technologies (e.g., AI, blockchain, IoT) influence the need for and the development of digital talent capabilities and their impact on organizational proactivity.
- iii. Explore the relationship between employee engagement in digital upskilling programs and organizational proactivity.
- iv. Identify and address barriers that organizations face in developing digital talent capabilities, particularly in resource-constrained environments.
- v. Investigate how small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) can develop digital talent capabilities to enhance their proactivity and competitiveness.
- vi. Examine the ROI of investments in digital talent capabilities and how this affects overall organizational performance and proactivity.
- vii. Study the interplay between digital talent capabilities, organizational agility, and proactivity, and how they collectively contribute to organizational success.

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